

METHODOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF USING DIDACTIC GAMES

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Abstract: This article reveals methods of effective organization of reading lessons for elementary school students. Examples of various didactic games intended for school teachers are given, and their rules and methods of application are described.

Key words: starter, method, style, reform, didactic game, pedagogical skill, domino.

Introduction.

Today's students are hungry for new things and get bored quickly. New approaches and colorful pedagogical methods are needed to keep them focused or to increase their interest in class. In other words, it is necessary to avoid homogeneity and falling into the same mold while preserving the achievements achieved in the field of education. It is the demand of the day to try to move from the type of education based on the development of human memory to the type aimed at the comprehensive development of human thinking, the practical application of the knowledge acquired by students, and the formation of practical skills and competencies in them. Only if this is achieved, the task of educating the young generation, which is the future of our country, can be solved rationally.

It's no secret that the right choice of educational methods and their appropriate use helps to ensure the effectiveness of education. Didactic games for primary school students are one of the types of activities that activate learning and form students' independent thinking, oral and written communication skills. Didactic games are one of the tools that increase students' interest in reading lessons. The purpose of the game is to arouse interest in education, science, and books. A didactic game arouses a lively interest in the cognitive process in children and helps them to receive information. Such games should be aimed at expanding, deepening, organizing children's imaginations about the environment, and developing their interests and abilities. In turn, this forms qualities such as being proud of our beautiful and rich mother tongue and respecting our moral values in students.

Also, the elements of the game serve to hide the didactic tasks from the children, thus easing the difficult learning process for them. Games with educational content, first of all simple interesting questions and answers on the subject, should be used in a certain part of the lesson. In this way, if games such as puzzles and quick telling are held regularly, students will accumulate certain skills. Accordingly, the skills and competences that students must acquire: the ability to describe, explain and predict. In the course of the lesson, it is necessary to clearly define the stages of tasks, rules and analysis of their results in the correct organization and conduct of games. Below are some examples of didactic games that are used in reading classes and have positive results.

"Co-authors" game.

The teacher reads the text or the students get to know the text independently.
Assignment:

- Come up with a continuation of the text. Think about what might happen in the future.
- Which of the heroes had the most influence on the events? How will the content of the work change if he does not participate?

- What event influenced the development of the plot?

"Let's draw a cartoon" game.

Students are divided into groups. They receive tasks written on cards, perform them and share ideas. For example, Aziza Akhmedova's theme "Winter's Tale" can be used as a transition. Assignment:

- What pictures should be drawn so that children who have not read the text of "Winter's Tale" can understand the content of the fairy tale?

- Choose the main ones that will help you to understand the content of the fairy tale from among the drawn pictures.

- Under the pictures, choose from the work or come up with your own captions.

"Make words from words" game.

It helps to increase students' vocabulary and enrich their vocabulary. Game conditions: Students are divided into 3 groups. A few words about the topic will be written down. Using the letters in the word, it is suggested to find and write words that have a different meaning without using any other letter. For example: in the fairy tale "Wise Boy" words are made from the word wise man. For example: mother, job, don, glory, niche, rest, dad, badge, car.

"Letter carrier" game.

The "Letter Carrier" student distributes invitations to groups of 4-5 people. Children identify where they were invited. For example: a farm, a park, a river, a school, a kitchen, a zoo. For each of these words, 5-6 words that differ in pronunciation and spelling are given with one letter removed. Students will have to read the appropriate words on their invitations, identifying the missing letter.

"Literary Museum" game.

The teacher organizes an imaginary trip through the halls of the "museum". Each hall is named according to the genre of the works. For example: now we will visit the "Hall of Fairy Tales" museum with you. There are magic items in this hall. Guess who they belong to. Seven branches ("Unity is great happiness"), khumcha ("Honesty"), bow ("Alpomish's childhood").

"Domino" (Find the word) game.

This game can be played in the introductory or reinforcing part of the lesson. The teacher says a word from the text, the students continue. If the word starts with the letter that the teacher ends with, the student should find and say the word that starts with this letter in the text. For example: if the teacher says the word Tashkent from the text "*Tashkent*" (*Erkin Malik*), students will find words such as *Takhtapul - Labzak - Kolob - Balkh - Khiva*.

"Who will find it faster?" game.

Students are divided into groups. The condition of the game: find words that have a certain meaning even if the first or last letter is removed. For example, in the fairy tale "The Tale of Stream Water" (Zohir Alam), they quickly find the words stream - moon, no - arrow, rich - moon, man - rest, winter - work, summer - little.

In conclusion, we can say that the information communication system is developing at a high level in today's world and based on the need for it, among other fields, to enter the

educational process and show its influence on its higher quality organization, it can be said that, it is very important for a primary teacher to have deep knowledge of techniques and technology, to be able to analyze and be knowledgeable and skilled at the level of innovation. For this, in the process of organizing a lesson, he should choose and use methods that are understandable, easy, and interesting for all students, use visual aids, apply newly produced technical tools, encourage students to work creatively and independently. It is desirable to use didactic games correctly and efficiently.

In the use of didactic games, it is necessary to look for a guaranteed result, choose modern and effective ways, and approach each thing and event as a complex. Otherwise, the activity will express traditionalism. From this point of view, the principles of any didactic game should be central. Only then the activity will be appropriate to the times, and the social order of the society can be fulfilled with honor.

In the organization of educational processes, in contrast to traditional methods, it is the need of the hour to master new pedagogical approaches and use them in the educational process. It is necessary to create a new atmosphere in the course of the lesson, to conduct it meaningfully using modern exhibitions and interactive methods.

Since elementary school students are prone to management, curious, and impressionable, the teacher is required to choose and use methods that are suitable for the age characteristics of the students, guarantee their easy mastery of the lesson, and solid learning of knowledge. will be done.

Using didactic games to determine the content of education, prepare the forms and tools of education, develop a system of assignments aimed at students' broad acquisition of knowledge and mastery of spiritual qualities, the result of education and the level of mastery determination organizes them like preparation of test tasks for objective assessment. The ability of free and independent thinking is formed in the course of reading lessons organized on the basis of didactic games of elementary school students. As a result of the formation of the ability to think independently, students are able to understand the laws of the world and society, as well as human qualities through the positive and negative characters in the work, in-depth study of knowledge, broad thinking, and the ability to make relevant decisions..

References:

1. Bakhtiyorovna, Adizova Nigora, and Ozodova Madina. "Technology Of Training." Aimed At Developing Creative Working Skills In The Training Of Primary School Teachers The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations 2021/3/31: 546-550.
2. Jobirovich Y. M. The Role Of Digital Technologies In Reform Of The Education System //The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. – 2021. – T. 3. – №. 04. – C. 461-
3. Amonov U. S. O'qish darslarida maqol janridan foydalanish usullari va ahamiyati: DOI: 10.53885/edinres. 2021.53. 34.124 US
4. O.R.Avezov. Ekstrennaya psixologicheskaya pomosh v ekstremalnih situatsiyax. Vestnik integrativnoy psixologii 4 (No. 21), 34-37.
5. Nigora Adizova Baxtiyorovna. 3-4-sinf ona tili darslarida qo'llanadigan tayanch kompetensiyalar. Journal of Advanced Research and Stability. Volume: 02 Issue: 01 | 2022

6. Rakhmonovich, Adizov Bakhtiyor, and Nodira Adizova Bakhtiyorovna. "linguistic classification of toponyms of bukhara district." Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL) 2.09 (2021): 1-
7. Safarov F. S. et al. The effect of a tissue biostimulator on embryonic and post-embryonic development of lambs //Uchen. Zap-azerb. sel'.-khodz-Inst. Ser. zhivot. – 1970. – №. 2. – C. 38-41.

